

International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research (IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online)
ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-5-sep-2014>

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DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF THE PHYSICAL SYSTEMS USING BOND GRAPH

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Abstract—Bond graph is used to analysis of Electrical and Mechanical system. Bond graph is a graphical technique for modeling and analysis of the any physical systems. The complex systems are analysis by using bond graph tool. In this paper the fundamental theory of bond graph and electro-mechanical model with simulation using symbol Shakti software is explored.

Keywords:- Bond graph, Iconic Diagram, Simulation, Symbol Shakti.

I. INTRODUCTION

Bond-Graph is a unified approach to the modeling of multi-disciplinary physical systems. It was formulated by Henry Paynter from MIT [Paynter 1961], brought to firm applicability by Karnopp from Davis University. By its nature of a power conserving description of a system, the Bond-Graph method is especially practical when several physical domains have to be modeled within a system simultaneously. This is certainly the case in mechatronics and robotics where mechanical, hydraulic, pneumatic and electrical systems in several combinations are present.

A. Bond Graph Theory

Bond graph is a graphical tool for comprehending the energetic structure of a physical system by representing the system by symbols and lines, thus identifying the power flow paths. The bond graph modeling language consists of power bonds with power direction, power variables, signal bonds, nine standard elements, causality analysis and much more.

The behavior of a real physical system is controlled by accumulation, dissipation and interchange of various forms of energy. The components or physical phenomena,

which make up a system, may be thought of as energy manipulators. Some elements will interact and exchange energy and their interaction points are called power ports. The power interaction between two ports is represented by a single line, the power bond, see Fig 1. A power bond is considered to conduct power instantaneously and without loss from one port to another.

Figure1. Basic Bonding

B. Bond Graph Elements

The standard form of a bond graph consists of 5 types of one port elements, 2 types of two port elements and 2 types of junctions as multiport elements to define their connections. One port element includes effort source (Se), flow source (Sf), capacitor (C), resistor (R) and inertia (I). One port elements are generalized versions of subsystems in real physical domains. The capacitor and the inertia are called storage elements; their function is to maintain the state of the system by maintaining the energy variables.

Two port elements. It includes transformers (TF) and gyrators (GY) which is used to conserve power. The transformer relates the effort to effort and the flow to flow between its two bonds and the gyrator relates flow to effort and effort to flow between its two bonds. Multi ports elements. It includes 0-junction and 1-junction. Bonds are representing by half arrow and its direction denotes the positive direction of power exchange between the components. A negative value of power indicates that the direction of power flow is opposite to the direction of

the bond. The detail of the each element is shown in table 1.

Table I. Basic bond graph elements [2]

Bond graph element	Name	Constitutive relations
$Se \xrightarrow{e}$	Effort source	$e = e(t)$
$Sf \xrightarrow{f}$	Flow source	$f = f(t)$
$\frac{e}{f} \xrightarrow{C}$	Capacitor	General : $q = \Phi_C(e)$ Linear : $q = Ce$
$\frac{e}{f} \xrightarrow{I}$	Inertia	General : $p = \Phi_I(f)$ Linear : $p = If$
$\frac{e}{f} \xrightarrow{R}$	Resistor	General : $e = \Phi_R(f)$ Linear : $e = Rf$
$\frac{e_1}{f_1} \xrightarrow{TF} \frac{e_2}{f_2}$	Transformer	$e_1 = e_2 m$ $f_1 m = f_2$
$\frac{e_1}{f_1} \xrightarrow{GY} \frac{e_2}{f_2}$	Gyrator	$e_1 = f_2 r$ $f_1 r = e_2$
$\frac{e_1}{f_1} \xrightarrow{0} \frac{e_2}{f_2}$	0-junction	$e_1 = e_2 = e_3$ $f_1 - f_2 - f_3 = 0$
$\frac{e_1}{f_1} \xrightarrow{1} \frac{e_2}{f_2}$	1-junction	$f_1 = f_2 = f_3$ $e_1 - e_2 - e_3 = 0$

C. Symbols Shakti

The SYMBOLS Shakti Bond pad is more users friendly and it is completely GUI driven. It includes a new equation optimization scheme and is an integrated development platform. The facilities for embedding models, equations and expressions in any document preparation software (like MS-WORD) are enhanced through exporting bitmap images and HTML code.

II. OBJECTIVE

The objective is to build a bond graph model of electro-mechanical system in which motor connected to flywheel using belt drive. The whole model is consisting of two systems electrical and mechanical. The input of the system is a voltage source and output is torque on flywheel shaft. The Bond graph model is developed by taking reference as an iconic diagram of the system. The diagram of a system is shown in fig. 2. According to the each component the connection bond is decided. The complete bond graph is then checked and by using simplification rule the final bond graph is plotted. After this the simulation is carried out and the result in the form of graph is obtained using Symbols Shakti.

Figure2. Diagram of System

A. Iconic diagram of system

Iconic diagram is the systematic representation of the engineering system. Consider the motor having the input as voltage source. The motor is having the inductance, electric resistance of the coil. Also motor has its own inertia and frictional resistance at the bearing. The iconic diagram of the motor consists of voltage source and the subcomponents of the motor. The system also consist the flexible belt and load (flywheel). The detail iconic diagram is shown in fig. 3.

Figure3. Iconic Diagram of System

This iconic diagram represents basic elements of the system. The basic element includes voltage source, inductor, motor, motor inertia, resistance at bearing, flexible belt and load. Now from this iconic representation the bond graph model of the system can be modeled using Symbols Shakti software. According to the elements of the system the components are interconnected by a bond.

III. BOND GRAPH MODEL

The bond graph model for the system is divided into two parts.

- Motor (Electrical)
- Transmission to flywheel (Mechanical)

Further the motor is divided into input voltage and actual motor. The input voltage is pass away from inductor and resistor and then to the motor. Therefore the bond graph of an input voltage includes electric potential (Se), inductor (I) and resistor (R). In case of motor the inertia of a motor (I) and the resistance at bearing (R) are taking into consideration. The mechanical part is divided into flexible belt (belt coefficient, Cb) and load (flywheel) inertia of load (I) and friction at shaft (R).

A. The complete bond graph

The bond graph for electrical and mechanical system is developed. The input to the system is voltage in the form of effort. The motor coefficient (mu) is used to convert effort into the angular velocity of the shaft by using gyrator (GY) element. The angular velocity is multiply by belt coefficient (Cb) by using transformer (TF). The torque of load shaft is calculated by using transformer. The complete bond graph of the system is shown in fig. 4.

Figure4. Complete Bond Graph of system

The system equations are

$$d(P14) = 1/\mu^2 * K12 * Q12 - R15 * P14 / M14$$

$$d(P6) = \mu_1 * P2 / M2 - R7 * P6 / M6 - \mu * K12 * Q12$$

$$d(P2) = SE1 - R3 * P2 / M2 - \mu_1 * P6 / M6$$

$$d(Q16) = P2 / M2$$

$$d(Q12) = \mu * P6 / M6 - 1/\mu^2 * P14 / M14$$

$$e13 = 1/\mu^2 * K12 * Q12$$

$$f13 = P14 / M14$$

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of the bond graph is possible with simulation used in *Symbols* software. For analysis the system, values of related terms are given in parameters table II. After this the x-axis and y-axis are defined. Then by setting time of 60 sec the simulator is being started. The simulator is run to observe the result of the system. The result is in the form of graph which shows the torque (N-m) of the load shaft, angular velocity (rad/sec) and torque (N-m) of the motor with respect to time. The result of analysis is shown in fig. 5, in that when the input voltage is 1V the respective torque on load shaft is 0.263 N-m, the torque of motor is 0.58 N-m and angular velocity of load shaft is 0.26 rad/sec. After 14.98 sec the torque of load shaft and torque of motor shaft is stable.

Figure 5. Results of Model

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper the study on the bond graph is presented. The importance of the bond graph for physical system is discussed. The modeling and simulation of the electro-mechanical system is done by using *Symbol Shakti* software.

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Table II. System Parameters

Parameters	Bondgraph Element	Value
Input Voltage	Se	1
Inductance	La	1
Resistance	Ra	1
Motor Constant	mu	0.7
Motor Inertia	J	1
Bearing Resistance	R	1
Belt co-efficient	Cb	1
Load inertia	J _l	1